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UKRAINOCENTRIC MASS MEDIA SYSTEM AS FACT AND FACTOR OF SYSTEMIC CHANGES IN UKRAINE

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The article deals with a relevant problem of creating Ukrainocentric mass media system in Ukraine. The system, which would be fully independent on political climate, created by corrupted oligarchic state power.

Top priority task, which is put forward by the author of this initiative, is to enlist the services of mass media and blog to UWIN in both Ukraine and diaspora, uniting them around common objective and common tasks: formation of strong and powerful Ukrainocentric mass media system which would play the key-role in Ukrainization of Ukraine information space, will become the decisive factor of raising national identity/conscience and civil responsibility of society, will prepare Ukraine and Ukrainian society for system changes. To attain this objective, the author considers it important to unite separate Ukrainocentric mass media and blogs in both Ukraine and diaspora, to create, on franchising basis, new information resources, based in Internet but with the perspective of real space existence.

The author offers to start developing such system on the basis of specially formed platform, which has got the title Ukrainian World Information Network (UWIN). UKRAINAINC.NET is offered to be the principal site, where one will publish: most important information, reviews and analytical publications about Ukraine and diaspora. The site will include two sections: the first one will incorporate Ukrainian mass media and blogs according to oblast; the second one will incorporate diaspora mass media and blogs according to the countries.

The author emphasizes the possibility of UWIN use for creative career self-actualization of journalists.

The agreement draft on this journalist community membership, which is voluntary and free of charge, is published. The network membership principles, directions and conditions of cooperation are stated and grounded.

Franchising as the basis for developing future Ukrainian World Information Network is discussed in a separate paragraph. It goes about the content of packages, which would include domain registration and service, trainings on working with sites, professional, journalistic and editorial education or re-qualification of Network members.

In Conclusions it is stressed that Ukrainocentric mass media system is one of the key, decisive facts and factors of system changes in Ukraine. Uniqueness of this project is that it considers information space of Ukraine in inseparable connection with information space of Ukrainian diaspora, that is with world information space.

Key words: *Ukraine information space, Ukrainocentric mass media system, Ukrainian World Information Network, information space Ukrainization, freedom of speech, creative self-actualization, franchising.*

УКРАЇНОЦЕНТРИЧНА СИСТЕМА ЗМІ ЯК ФАКТ І ФАКТОР СИСТЕМНИХ ЗМІН В УКРАЇНІ

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Стаття присвячена актуальній проблемі створення в Україні україноцентричної системи засобів масової інформації (ЗМІ). Такої, яка була б повністю незалежна від політичного клімату, створюваного корумпованою олігархічною владою.

Першочерговим завданням, яке поставлене автором цієї ініціативи, є залучити до участі в УСІМ україноцентричні ЗМІ та блогерів, в Україні та в діаспорі суціль, об'єднуючи їх навколо спільної мети і спільних завдань: створення потужної україноцентричної системи ЗМІ, яка відіграє ключову роль в українізації інформаційного простору України, стане вирішальним чинником піднесення національної свідомості та громадянської відповідальності суспільства й підготує Україну й українське суспільство до системних змін.

Досягнення такої мети автор вбачає в тому, щоб зібрати в єдине ціле окремі україноцентричні ЗМІ та блоги в Україні та діаспорі, а також на основі франчайзингу створювати нові інформаційні ресурси, базовані в Інтернеті та з перспективою виходу в реальний простір.

Розпочинати розбудовувати таку систему пропонується на спеціально створеній платформі, що отримала назву Українська Світова Інформаційна Мережа (УСІМ). Головним сайтом мережі бачиться згаданий UKRAINAINC.NET, на якому публікуватимуться: найважливіша інформація, огляди й аналітичні матеріали про Україну та діаспору. Сайт матиме два розділи: перший об'єднуватиме ЗМІ та блоги України за областями; другий — об'єднуватиме ЗМІ та блоги діаспори за країнами.

Окремо йдеться про платформу УСІМ як можливість творчої кар'єрної самореалізації журналістів.

Публікується для обговорення проект угоди про членство в цій журналістській спільноті, яке є добровільним і безкоштовним. Обґрунтовуються принципи членства в Мережі та напрями й умови співпраці.

Окремим пунктом розглядається франчайзинг як основа розбудови майбутньої Української Світової Інформаційної Мережі. Йдеться про зміст пакетів, які включатимуть реєстрацію та обслуговування доменів, тренінги з роботи над сайтами, фахову журналістську й редакторську підготовку чи перепідготовку членів Мережі тощо.

У висновках наголошується, що україноцентрична система ЗМІ є одним із ключових, вирішальних фактів і факторів системних змін в Україні. Унікальність цього проекту це й у тому, що він розглядає інформаційний простір України у нерозривному зв'язку з інформаційним простором української діаспори, а отже — і світовим інформаційним простором.

Ключові слова: Інформаційний простір України, україноцентрична система ЗМІ, українська світова інформаційна мережа, українізація інформаційного простору, свобода слова, творча самореалізація, франчайзинг.

To the greatest extent we as experts are concerned with the Ukrainian information space formation and a national information product development.

In this regard, one should look at the results of our work over the years of Ukraine's independence. How sad it is, but we have to admit that in this field we have nothing to boast of. Our information space is monopolized by Russian or pro-Russian propaganda. Information sovereignty of Ukraine is under threat. It is extremely difficult for Ukrainian information product to break through to the consumer, and the quality of it leaves much to desire: it is not competitive.

The executive, legislative and judicial powers of Ukraine have done little, and there is little that can be done in the area that is of the society's responsibility. The only thing they have to do is to ensure the free functioning of the media and the protection of journalists, but they do not, to put it mildly, do it in the right way.

In particular, the laws concerning fixing a quota for Ukrainian product in (non) Ukrainian mass media of Ukraine, which actually do not work, became a proverb. In the end, from this situational legislation, one should not hope for a positive result in conditions that require systemic changes. It is no coincidence that the systematic Ukrainization of the information space is not even discussed.

Of course, I remember the oligarchic nature of the Russian and pro-Russian media owners, their media managers, as well as the "stars" (aslanias, kiseliovs, muraievs, shusters or whoever they are).

It is obvious that in Ukraine there is a rather large group of Ukrainian-indifferent, Ukrainian-phobic and Ukrainian-hating journalists and «journalists», who exchange their word and their conscience for the "Golden Taurus" or even simply for the opportunity to blush on the TV screen. There are a number of them.

However, I know that in Ukraine there are also quite a lot of decent and honest, Ukrainocentric journalists and media managers, for whom the Ukrainization of the information space is not just a dream but a matter of life. Some of them, by their strengths and capabilities, handle their field, and someone just does not know where and how to start.

Many of them live in hopes and hope that the Ukrainian government will wake up, recollect them and call them on the information front to fight for their already successful Ukraine. Some of my colleagues are happy with their hopes for a "resolution or law" that will help us to create a Ukrainocentric system of mass media. I would not want to disappoint them, but I have to: the information sphere is not the field where the government would be interested in solving problems.

The information space, even the information sovereignty of Ukraine, is the Ukrainian society's and each individual citizen's sphere of responsibili-

ty. And journalists and media managers, like anyone else, must not only be aware of this, but also be proactive and entrepreneurial in this field.

For a long time, I call for the creation in Ukraine of a Ukrainocentric system of mass media, completely independent on the political climate created by corrupt oligarchic authorities. Sometimes, journalists from Ukraine write to me: try to go and register a media anywhere in Ukraine... I know this only well, in particular from my own experience too, albeit from the old one. At the same time, I am sure: this problem is solvable, and it is not necessary to address it somewhere in Ukraine to resolve this issue.

The subject of this article is just one of the possible options for the creation of a Ukrainocentric system of mass media and the Ukrainization of the information space.

Let us consider some aspects of this task.

I. Make journalism and means of mass media in Ukraine "The fourth power"

Our goal: To create a network of Ukrainocentric mass media and to integrate them into a media system capable of becoming a "fourth power".

Our tasks:

1. Ukrainization of the information space.
2. Protection of informational sovereignty of Ukraine.
3. Raising national consciousness and civil responsibility of Ukrainian society.
4. Formation of public opinion and ensuring its effective influence on the executive, legislative and judicial branches of political power.
5. Facilitating the establishment and development of Ukrainocentric journalistic science, education.
6. Information provision of fruitful cooperation of Ukraine with the diaspora and effective participation of world Ukrainians in Ukrainian nation-building and state-building activities.

To achieve the stated goal and to fulfil the above-mentioned tasks, we want to gather separate Ukrainocentric mass media and blogs in Ukraine and the Diaspora in a single fist, as well as to create new information resources based on franchising, based on the Internet and with the prospect of access to real space under favorable circumstances.

We do not offer ready to eat fish and bread. We offer rods and a network that should cover Ukrainocentric informational products throughout the territory of Ukraine and the diaspora at different levels — national, regional and local. Together with the necessary support.

That is why we have prepared a platform on which we can begin to develop a Ukrainocentric system of mass media in Ukraine bypassing those obstacles that exist or may arise there. This platform is called the Ukrainian Worldwide Information Network (UWIN). Here is our site: <http://www.>

ukrainainc.net. Waiting for its turn is the second resource: <http://www.ukrainainc.tv>.

The matter depends on Ukrainocentric journalists and bloggers. Go to the above link to the site, get acquainted with the terms of cooperation, write to us and get to work.

No one, except us and you, will do this.

The question arises: how to do it?

II. UKRAINIAN WORLDWIDE INFORMATION NETWORK

The idea of creating a global network of Ukrainocentric media is not new. This idea, in the 1990's, was brought to me, as the head of the Union of Journalists of Ukraine Kyiv Organization, by a veteran of Ukrainian journalism whose name was Mr. Mirsky. More than once I went back to this idea, thinking of ways and possibilities of its implementation in both general outlines and in details.

The events of recent years make the implementation of this project urgent. I hope that in Ukraine and in the diaspora there will be enough nationally conscious and civically advanced journalists and bloggers who will respond to my call and take part in this matter of extraordinary importance.

In present day situation, creating a network of Ukrainocentric media seems to me possible under the following conditions.

FIRST: rally of Ukrainocentric media and bloggers around a special site created for this project. Their sites and blogs will be presented with relevant information and linked to this site.

SECOND: working out the foundations of the association of Ukrainocentric media and bloggers, on the basis of which we will sign bilateral cooperation agreements with each media and blogger, and later — multilateral ones.

For this, we will prepare and offer for discussion the principles of the formation of the system, its ideology, methodology, organizational and managerial basis, etc.

THIRD: the experience of the association of current media and blogs journalists will show us the ways and means of building and strengthening the systems.

Based on the needs and the state of affairs, we chose the optimal forms of expansion of the system (eg, franchising), as well as the technological and financial support of the participants.

The working languages should be Ukrainian and — outside of Ukraine — the language of the country in which the media or blog is located.

The main site of the network is the above mentioned website UKRAINAINC.NET, which will publish: the most important information, reviews and analytical materials about Ukraine and the diaspora.

One of the sections of the site (or sites of the second level) will combine media and blogs of Ukraine by regions. The second one — will combine media and diaspora blogs by region.

By combining internet (online) and non-Internet (offline) forms, in the long run we will come to creation of a full-fledged media that will be independent from the government, on the one hand, and Ukrainian oligarchs on the other one.

We will rely solely on community support and on Ukrainocentric sponsors, following the best practices of public and private media.

The scientific base, as well as the training and retraining of journalists, will be provided by the Ukrainian University and affiliated scientific and educational institutions in Ukraine and abroad.

III. UWIN as an opportunity for journalists of creative and self-realization.

The discussion of the project in social networks encouraged me to highlight the theme of UWIN as an opportunity for professional development and career growth of Ukrainocentric journalists, bloggers, media managers in Ukraine and the diaspora.

The fact is that, as it was mentioned before, in such cases I began to receive inquiries and suggestions regarding the work on the Internet for hiring, but also with the possibility of ... emigration. And they come from quite serious people.

Who carefully reads my publications, he probably understands that I am not a supporter of the mass emigration of Ukrainians from Ukraine. On the contrary, since the establishment of the Ukraine Citizens International Association (1997), I am focused on the idea of returning Ukrainians to their "Promised Land" and building up a successful independent Ukraine.

The business that I am engaged in and this Ukrainian Worldwide Information Network project, of course, do not preclude the creation of opportunities for unlimited travel of Ukrainians around the world, including for long-term work beyond the borders of Ukraine.

Probably, in due course, UWIN will have the needs and opportunities for hiring specialists from Ukraine to work in the USA or other countries of the world, since it is their knowledge and experience that will be needed to carry out the tasks that the Network will face at that time.

We are just starting out, and we have no possibilities or needs for it now.

Finally, I would like to emphasize that the very idea and purpose of its implementation is not limited to creating the maximum possible number of jobs and, consequently, pay people wages.

It goes, first of all, about the possibilities for self-realization of Ukrainians, in our case — journalists, bloggers, media managers, to help them «make themselves», and therefore — make money.

Each member of the Network, of course, in the long run can become an employer, who will open jobs for those who simply want to fulfil the task entrusted to him or her by the manager.

How do we imagine the realization of the creative and career opportunities of those who want to become a member of UWIN?

The grounds for membership, the directions and conditions of cooperation, the rights and obligations of the parties in general terms are outlined in the draft of the proposed agreement (see below).

This is the document that will be further refined, deepened, and detailed, but it already gives a general idea of how and what we should do to create, establish and develop our Network as the backbone of the Ukrainocentric system of mass media.

The primary goal we set for ourselves is to involve to UWIN Ukrainian-centered media and bloggers in Ukraine and in the diaspora, by joining them around our common goal and our common tasks: creating a powerful Ukrainocentric media system that plays a key role in the Ukrainization of the information space of Ukraine, will become a decisive factor in the rise of national consciousness and civil responsibility of society and will prepare Ukraine and Ukrainian society for systemic changes.

We are aware that due to different objective and subjective reasons, one such association will not be enough: in Ukraine and the diaspora there exist too few Ukrainocentric mass media and blogs, even the combined efforts of which will be not enough to meet the challenges, to solve the existing problems and to achieve goals which were set.

The second direction that UWIN will actively develop is the creation and support of new media and blogs that will be independent entities of the Web, even though they will use our logo and other attributes.

In order to preserve the unity of the ideological and thematic orientation and the affinity of the functional forms of the Web, we chose franchising as the basis for the development of the Network (see details below).

This means that we will provide members of the Network with assistance in registering a domain, setting up and maintaining a website, consulting and methodological assistance, supporting with information and analytical materials, facilitating professional journalistic and editorial training or further education, etc.

Membership in the Network is the first step to mastering other tops. If you are interested in participating in our project, join us with your site or blog or try to create your own information-analytical resource — a site or a blog.

Over time, having completed the first organizational phase, we will solve the problem of our activities at the national, regional and district levels.

Hopefully, journalists and bloggers will appear who will be able to take on the role of coordinators so that to present themselves as media managers too.

It is now very important for our tomorrow's partners and the participants of the Network to understand the most important thing: the priority for us is to create a Ukrainocentric system of mass media for Ukraine and world Ukrainians. The realization of the creative potential and satisfaction of the

ambitions of each journalist should be subordinated to this goal, and not vice versa.

IV. UWIN MEMBERSHIP AGREEMENT

(Draft)

Ukrainian Worldwide Information Network (UWIN) membership is voluntary and free of charge.

UWIN membership is open to all Ukrainocentric media (newspapers, magazines, TV and radio channels), as well as bloggers who meet the requirements set out below:

1. PRINCIPLES OF NETWORK MEMBERSHIP

1.1. Ukrainocentricity.

1.2. The Ukrainian language as a prerequisite for mass media and blogging from Ukraine.

1.3 The Ukrainian language and language of the country of location for diaspora mass media and blogs.

1.4. Transparency of legal ownership. We shall sign a cooperation agreement only with media owners and bloggers, and if the media or blog belongs to a public organization – with the relevant organization.

1.5. To join the network, authorized persons provide: (a) basic information about the media or blog; (b) biographical information about the owner or manager of the media or blog.

1.6. A media or a blog joins the Network after signing a bilateral association agreement on cooperation on the basis of association, that is, with the right of presentation in the advisory bodies of the Network (eg, the Supervisory Board, the Editorial Board, etc.), when such bodies are envisaged.

1.7. Mass media and blogs with state ownership or belonging to political parties can not be part of our Network. Cooperation with such media and blogs will be conducted on a separate business-to-business basis.

1.8. A participant can leave the Network at any time by announcing his intention to the UWIN Coordination Center.

1.9. UWIN reserves the right to exclude from a network a one who does not comply with the network's requirements and its obligations before the Network.

2. DIRECTIONS AND CONDITIONS OF COOPERATION

Cooperation between the Network and its participants is carried out on both a non-commercial and commercial basis.

2.1. Non-profit activities

Non-commercial information co-operation is the main type of cooperation and expects that the parties (UWIN and a participant) undertake the following obligations:

2.1.1. UWIN :

2.1.1.1. Welcomes every new member with the presentation on the home page of the site

2.1.1.2. Places the participant's logo with a reference to the site / blog on the corresponding page of the site

2.1.1.3. Periodically presents selected publications on the relevant pages of the site that may be of interest for the entire Network.

2.1.1.4. UWIN members' banners are placed on UWIN website on an exchange or on a commercial basis

2.1.2. MEMBER:

2.1.2.1. Places on the site or blog the UWIN logo with the Internet address of its site

2.1.2.2. Provides detailed information on his / her site as a one-time presentation of the Network

2.1.2.3. Periodically, on the relevant pages of his / her site or blog, the member presents recommended non-commercial materials for distributing throughout the Network as well as selected publications from our site or from the sites of other members of the Network that may be of interest to the readers of the site or the blog of the participant.

2.2. Commercial activity

2.2.1. Commercial cooperation between the Network and individual participants may be based on separate bilateral agreements in such areas as:

- advertising and information activities;
- other activities mentioned on the ukrainainc.com site.

2.2.2. The use of non-profit information materials of the Network by individual participants for the purpose of obtaining profit entails financial penalties (fines) that the offending participant has to pay to the Network and / or other participant of the Network whose copyright has been violated.

2.2.3. In case of the violator's refusal to pay a fine or repeated violation, the offender will be removed from the Network.

3. FINAL PROVISIONS

3.1. UWIN is responsible only in the following cases:

- as a subject of commercial activity in accordance with the legislation of the country of location;
- on obligations of bilateral agreements signed with individual participants of the Network.

3.2. UWIN has no responsibilities on multilateral and bilateral obligations of individual members of the Network, if UWIN is not a party to the relevant agreement.

3.3. With the growth of the Network and the costs of managing the UWIN site and the coordination of the Network, in the long run, the introduction of annual membership fees and / or fees for the processing of the incoming information is possible.

3.4. UWIN is interested in creating and expanding national, regional, city and district blogs, online TV and radio programs in Ukraine as well as regional and local ones in countries of compact settlement of Ukrainian

Diaspora, on the basis of franchising, providing appropriate professional assistance in the creation and development of new media and blogs.

3.4.1. For this purpose, UWIN will offer several packages that will include domain registration and service, training on working with sites, professional journalistic and editorial training or re-training of UWIN members, etc.

3.4.2. Franchise projects are executed by separate agreements.

For Ukraina, Inc. / UWIN —

Volodymyr Ivanenko, President

Tel: 1-240-432-3307

e-mail: ukrainainc@yahoo.com

For a UWIN member — [Website Title or Blog.]

[Name and surname of the owner or person acting on his / her behalf.]

Tel .:

e-mail:

Note:

The full details of the Parties are specified in the bilateral commercial agreements, which are considered as a part of this broad agreement.

V. FRANCHISING AS THE BASIS FOR UWIN DEVELOPMENT

The Ukrainian Worldwide Information Network (UWIN) is interested in creating and expanding national, regional, city and district sites, blogs, online TV and radio studios in Ukraine, as well as regional and local ones in the countries of compact settlement of Ukrainian Diaspora on the basis of franchising with the provision of proper professional assistance in the creation and development of new media and blogs.

For this purpose, UWIN will offer several packages that will include domain registration and service, training for working out sites, professional journalistic and editorial training or re-training of Network members, etc.

Package No 1 includes:

- 1) domain registration;
- 2) the website setup;
- 3) help in the website servicing;
- 4) consulting and methodic assistance;
- 5) support with information and analytical materials.

Package No 2 includes:

- 1) domain registration;
- 2) the website setup;
- 3) help in the website servicing;
- 4) consulting and methodic assistance;
- 5) support with information and analytical materials;
- 6) editing and proofreading of the author's website materials of the.

Package No 3 includes:

- 1) domain registration;
- 2) the website setup;

- 3) help in the website servicing;
- 4) consulting and methodic assistance;
- 5) support with information and analytical materials;
- 6) professional journalistic and editorial training or advanced training.
(We do not publish the cost of individual Network packages at this time.)

ADVERTISING & OTHER COMMERCIAL ACTIVITIES

The franchisee pays UWIN 10% of the revenue received from advertising and other types of commercial activity on his / her website.

When acting as an advertising agent or intermediary in other commercial operations of the Network, the franchisee receives 15% of the commission on the value of the attracted advertisements or other commercial transaction.

LEGAL ASPECTS

Ukraina, Inc. and the UWIN, do not act as an employer in relation to a franchisees and have no obligations as an employer to them.

Franchisees can not position themselves as full-time employees of Ukraina, Inc., and UWIN in particular.

The franchisees are private entrepreneurs as individuals or as representatives of legal entities established by them.

Franchisees are subjects of local law in countries and regions of their business activity and residence — regardless of whether they act as legal or physical persons.

Conclusions

1. The Ukrainocentric media system is one of the key, decisive facts and factors of systemic changes in Ukraine.

2. We are late with the formation of such media system for a quarter of a century, but it's never too late to start its creation and development.

3. Obviously, there are many options and ways to implement the idea. It is important that the paths chosen by us lead to the desired result.

4. Ukrainian Worldwide Information Network is one of the options that makes it possible to create a mass media system without the participation of large capital as a private or public initiative.

5. The uniqueness of this project is that it considers Ukraine's information space as being inextricably linked to the information space of the Ukrainian diaspora, and hence the world's information space.

6. In forming the media system of Ukraine as a part of the Ukrainian Worldwide Information Network, we see an important factor of ensuring freedom of speech, the rights and freedoms of Ukrainian journalists and bloggers, as well as opportunities for their creative self-realization.

Washington, USA
September 15, 2018